

Combined impacts of global change and silver nanoparticle exposure on freshwater biofilm functioning

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Abstract

Emerging pollutants like engineered nanoparticles (ENPs) pose significant threats to aquatic ecosystems, particularly under the intensifying pressures of climate warming. However, the combined effects of these stressors on water quality and ecosystem functionality remain poorly understood. This study explored the interactive impacts of silver-containing nanoparticles (Ag NPs, Ag₂S NP) and silver nitrate (AgNO₃, ionic control) on fluvial biofilms, using recirculating mesocosms at two temperatures (18 °C and 25 °C). Key ecological functions, such as primary production and nutrient cycling, were evaluated through water and ENP property analyses, alongside biofilm structural and functional assessments after 1, 3, 15, and 30 days, allowing to quantify acute and chronic impacts.

Out of 24 parameters measured, 54.2% exhibited additive effects across treatments, while synergistic responses were observed in AgNP+T°C and Ag₂SNP+T°C treatments, and antagonistic effects were noted in AgNO₃+T°C. Higher temperatures (25 °C) amplified microbial metabolism and nutrient cycling activity, resulting in decreased total carbon (TC) and increased total nitrogen (TN) and phosphate (TP) levels. Ag NP exposure further heightened TC and TN, likely due to enhanced cell mortality and extracellular polysaccharide release. Interestingly, Ag₂S NP flumes showed increased phosphatase activity, correlating with reduced TP and diminished biofilm glucosidase activity.

These findings highlight the compounded (synergistic) detrimental effects of silver ENPs and warming on freshwater biofilms, underscoring their pivotal role in nutrient recycling and water quality maintenance. The study emphasizes the urgent need to integrate combined pollutant and climate scenarios into environmental risk assessments to safeguard ecosystem integrity under future climate conditions.

Key words

Multi-stressor interactions, silver nanoparticles, environmental ageing, aquatic toxicity, global warming, temperature, mesocosms, antagonistic and synergistic effects.

Highlights

- Silver particles have different impacts on biofilm than silver ions.
- Silver sulfide ENP cause an increase of phosphatase enzyme activity while a decrease in β -glucosidase.
- After 3 days (acute period) biofilms were able to cope with the silver toxicity. Despite the significant $Ag_{acc.}$ in the biofilms exposed to AgNP, neither ENPs nor free Ag^+ ions were able to consistently affect the selected enzymes (i.e., Glu, Pho, Leu and photosystem II (PSII)); but generate an EPS increase.
- After 30 days (chronic period), respiration was clearly reduced in both AgNP (23%) and $AgNO_3$ (15%) flumes as compared to control and Ag_2S NP flumes.
- Microbial communities gradually become more heterotrophic with warming, with implications at the functional ecosystem level
- ΔT can greatly influence the vulnerability of autotrophic and heterotrophic biofilm communities to metal toxicity

Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems are threatened by multiple environmental stressors including the exposure to a plethora of environmental pollutants as well as the impacts of global change, such as the increase of temperature. Over the last decades, the use of ENP has increased rapidly due to their unique properties and extremely wide range of applications in industry, agriculture, biomedicine, biology, water treatment and remediation (Albalawi et al., 2021; Bathi et al., 2022; Rudramurthy & Swamy, 2018). As a consequence, the release of ENPs into the environment has been accelerating (Bathi et al., 2022; Giese et al., 2018; Gottschalk et al., 2013). While considerable progress has been made in understanding the individual ecological impact of many of these environmental stressors, the combined impacts of emerging pollutants (e.g., engineered nanoparticles; ENPs) and global change related stressors on ecosystems remains poorly understood. Furthermore, to date, most toxicity studies have been conducted under controlled laboratory conditions (e.g., small microcosms like jars or indoor channels), often using unrealistically high concentrations (McGillicuddy et al., 2017) relative to the real environmental concentrations. Given the constraints of such small-scale approaches, larger experimental systems (e.g., mesocosms) are needed to explore and better understand complex community composition and their effects at ecosystem level.

Impacts of pollution and climate stresses are of particular concern for aquatic microbial communities, particularly biofilms, which perform crucial roles in freshwater ecosystems by driving stream carbon respiration, primary production and nutrient (re)cycling (Battin et al., 2016; Boulêtreau et al., 2014; Findlay, 2010; Majdi et al., 2013; Romani A.M., Sabater, 2001). Biofilms are the basal resource of the food web in aquatic ecosystems, and are highly sensitive to temperature changes (Romani et al., 2008). Therefore, projected warming in freshwater ecosystems could profoundly impact the structure and functioning of biofilm communities, along with the essential ecosystems services they provide. The combined effects of rising temperatures and pollution-related stressors could exacerbate these impacts, potentially leading to catastrophic consequences for these vital ecosystems.

Silver nanoparticles (AgNP) are among the most widespread ENP currently in use due to their antibacterial properties, making them suitable for use in a wide range of personal care and healthcare products. Their high electrical and thermal conductivity additionally drives their widespread use in electronic devices. The environmental behaviour of AgNPs, including

dissolution to release silver ions, their bioavailability, dominant transformation/dissolution products, and equilibrium concentration in aquatic environments are controlled by their properties such as their size, shape and coating (Reidy et al., 2013; Zhang, Hu, & Deng, 2016). Dissolution and release of ions are considered to be the main driver of their antimicrobial properties, but “particle-specific” effects arising from direct physical contact with membranes and biomolecules, shading and blockage for example, cannot be excluded (Behra et al., 2013; Zhang, Hu, & Deng, 2016). Besides their antibacterial effects, toxicological effects have been observed in other aquatic organisms such as algae, fungi, micro and macroinvertebrates and fish albeit at higher concentrations than those predicted to occur in the environment (Fabrega et al., 2011; Navarro et al., 2008; Tlili et al., 2016; 2017). However, effects of ENP on complex microbial communities and their ecological interactions and ecosystem processes remain unclear.

The large surface area of ENP makes them highly reactive, meaning that they are easily transformed through interaction with biotic and abiotic constituents of their environment characterisation of these transformations is essential such that observed ecotoxicological impacts can be correlated with the “environmental aged” form of the ENP (Tortella et al., 2020). In the case of Ag NPs, a typical transformation in sewage systems and in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) is the reaction with sulphide to form silver sulphide nanoparticles (Ag_2S NP) (Kampe et al., 2018; Kent et al., 2014; Kühr et al., 2018). Toxic effects from aged Ag_2S NPs are expected to be lower than for Ag NPs, as Ag_2S NPs have extremely low solubility under oxic conditions which reduces the bioavailability of Ag^+ (Levard et al., 2013; Thalmann et al., 2014; Zhang, Hu, Li, et al., 2016a), and thus decreases Ag_2S NPs toxicity relative to their pristine (Ag NPs) counterparts (Levard et al., 2013; Thalmann et al., 2014; Zhang, Hu, Li, et al., 2016b), although toxicity to soil microorganisms has been observed (Peixoto et al., 2020, 2022). Nevertheless, there is a rapid release of Ag^+ from Ag_2S NPs under light irradiation in the presence of Fe(iii) and/or when treated by oxidants such as free chlorine, manganese oxide and ozone imply that Ag_2S NP stability and safety may be overestimated requiring further consideration of impacts of transformation of Ag_2S -NPs toxicity in freshwater ecosystems (He et al., 2019; Li et al., 2016; Shi et al., 2018).

In addition to increasing pollution burdens, ecosystems are increasingly stressed by accelerating global warming. Climate models predict that global average temperatures will rise between 1.5 °C and 4.5 °C before 2050 (IPCC, Summary for Policymakers - Special Report. IPCC Press Release

2018/24/PR (2018)). Water temperature is expected to increase by 0.3 – 0.9 °C for each degree increase in air temperature depending on the surface water source, and additional increases in water temperature of up to 6 °C are anticipated if shading by riparian vegetation is lost (Rosa et al., 2013). Even higher increases of water temperature are likely to occur locally under low flow conditions, with potentially devastating effects on freshwater ecosystems (Kathol et al., 2009). While the effects of increased water temperature on physicochemical conditions (e.g., dissolved oxygen) and processes at the organism level (e.g., respiration, growth, feeding, enzymatic activities, decomposition) are well known (Hester & Doyle, 2011), the impacts of temperature on the environmental behavior and transformations of engineered nanoparticles (ENPs) remain largely unknown, as do the combined effects of ENPs and increased temperature on the composition and function of freshwater microbial communities, which are critical to the health of freshwater ecosystems.

To address these critical and urgent knowledge gaps regarding a vital freshwater ecosystem, in this study, we investigated the effects of exposure to silver ENP – Ag NP as pristine and Ag₂S NP as a representative of an “aged” ENP – under current and predicted warmer temperatures at microbial community and ecosystem levels. An outdoor mesocosms system was used to explore acute and chronic responses of the whole biofilm community to silver ENP (both pristine AgNPs and a chemically aged counterpart, Ag₂S NPs) under different temperatures, using a broad set of end-points as an integrated approach. Inclusion of the ionic form of silver (silver nitrate, AgNO₃) as an ionic control allows us to understand the effect of ionic vs. nanoparticle toxicity since the Ag₂S NPs are expected to have a much lower release of Ag⁺ compared to the Ag NPs. If ENP dissolution occurs after uptake by biofilms there is the potential for a much higher local Ag⁺ concentration compared to direct uptake of dissolved Ag⁺ which has been described as a “Trojan horse” effect.

The following three hypotheses were tested: (i) pristine (Ag NP) and aged ENPs (Ag₂S NP) have different impacts on the biofilm community related to their different abilities to shed Ag⁺ ions, with the potential toxicity of Ag NP expected to be higher than that of the Ag₂S NP (due to their low solubility of Ag₂S NPs); (ii) increased temperature will have both (a) biological effects, increasing biofilm metabolism (e.g., respiration), and (b) physicochemical effects on silver ENP (AgNP and Ag₂S NP), modifying their transformations (e.g., increasing their dissolution in water), thus causing them to have higher potential negative effects on biofilms; and (iii) the combination

of both stressors (silver and T°) will have greater impact than simply adding the two effects together, as a result of synergistic effects and different modes of action of the two stressors (silver and T°) on the biofilms.

Material and Methods

2.1. The mesocosm setup and experimental design.

Controlled exposure experiments were carried out in the Environmental Change Outdoor Laboratory (EcoLaboratory) at the University of Birmingham. In this experiment, 40 recirculating flumes (length, 2 m; width, 0.42 m; depth, 0.15 m) were used and the bottom of each flume was covered with a single layer of commercially available pea gravel (1:1 mixture of 20 and 10 mm gravel); 150 glass microscope slides (75 x 25 mm) were distributed across the gravel surface to facilitate biofilm colonization and to be used as sampling units, as shown in the Supplementary Information (SI Fig. 1). Before the start of the experiment, all materials, including the recirculating flumes, pea gravel and glass slides, were rinsed with nitric acid (10%). The flumes were placed under a white tarpaulin tent to avoid dilution during rainfall events. The light intensity was on average 68.10 ± 20.4 (maximum 341.15 ± 9.7) $\mu\text{mol photons m}^2/\text{s}$ (natural light) and the water flow velocity in the flumes was around 0.2 m/s (driven by a pump in each flume). The flume experiments used dechlorinated mains water, 60 L each flume. A heater in each flume was used to maintain the water temperature, with 20 flumes heated to around 18 °C (cool - T °C), simulating current freshwater system temperatures, while the temperature of the other 20 flumes was set at around 25°C (warm - ΔT °C), simulating warm freshwater temperatures. Under these conditions, mesocosm systems were colonised by introducing 10 mL of homogenised aliquots of a fluvial biofilm (OD \approx 0.5) in each of 40 flumes obtained from scraping different cobbles from the Bourn Brook stream (Birmingham UK - 52.446022, -1.958960). New inoculum was provided weekly to each flume during the first three weeks of the total 4 weeks of colonization. The established biofilms were subsequently exposed to different concentrations of engineered silver nanoparticles (ENP) or ionic silver for 4 additional weeks.

The AgNP used were polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) coated within a mean size of 60 nm supplied by Amepox to the Horizon 2020 [NanoFASE](#) project as a representative pristine ENP (these ENP were used and described in Silva et al. (2020)). The Ag₂S NP were generated from a sub-sample of the AgNPs by reacting the particles with Na₂S under vigorous stirring in accordance with the procedure previously reported (Kim et al., 2010). The Ag₂S particles are considered to be

representative of aged Ag NPs, mimicking the output of wastewater treatment processes, and were determined to have a median size of 30 nm (SI Fig. 2). Briefly, 400 mL of AgNPs suspension was poured into a 500 mL mixture of 1 mM Na₂S and 10 mM NaNO₃ under vigorous stirring at room temperature for 24 hours. The NPs were isolated by centrifugation at 7,000 g for one hour, and the resulting Ag₂S NPs were kept in 50 mL H₂O and stored at 4 °C until use. More information about the characterisation of the ENP is presented in the SI Fig. 2-4. Moreover, two different controls were used, one group without any form of silver (untreated control) and the other treated with silver nitrate (AgNO₃) as the ionic control to allow distinction between impacts from dissolved (Ag⁺) versus particulate silver. For each treatment 5 flumes were used (quintuplicate) with each flume representing an experimental unit. Concentrations used were 50 µg of the Ag NP/L and AgNO₃/L and 25 µg Ag₂S NP/L based on the Ag stoichiometry. The factorial design is summarised in Table 1.

In order to avoid nutrient depletion in the flumes and to maintain constant silver concentrations throughout the exposure phase of the experiment, the water of each flume was renewed weekly during both the colonisation and exposure periods. Flumes were emptied using peristaltic pumps set at a low rate to avoid affecting the biofilms and refilled with dechlorinated mains water. The silver treatments (Ag NP, Ag₂S NP and AgNO₃) were spiked directly into each flume close to the recirculation pump to ensure rapid mixing. The mains water had phosphate concentrations above the threshold for nutrient limitation (i.e., P ≈ 250 µg/L) so no supplemental phosphate was needed. Water and biofilm samples were collected for analysis at multiple time points: before the addition of silver (time 0 hours), and after 1 and 3 days (acute exposure), as well as 15 and 30 days (chronic exposure).

2.2. Physicochemical analyses

Water quality parameters in each flume were measured *in situ* at all sampling times. Temperature was measured every 15 min for the duration the study using thermistors (Campbell Scientific, North Logan, UT, U.S.A.) connected to a Campbell Scientific CR1000 datalogger. Dissolved oxygen (DO) were measured using a ProODO probe (YSI, Yellow Springs, USA) and pH and conductivity using handheld metres (HI 98129/HI 98130 Hanna) in each flume before and after each water renewal. Water samples (15 mL) were collected at each measurement time (0, 1, 3, 15 and 30 days) for total organic carbon (TOC) and total nitrogen (TN) analysis using a Shimadzu TOC-L CPH with ASI-L. Total phosphorus (TP) was analysed using inductively coupled

plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, Agilent 7500ce). Anions (Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) and cations (K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) were analysed using ion-chromatography (Dionex ICS1100). Size (nm) and zeta potential (mV) of the ENPs once they were in the flumes were analysed by dynamic light scattering (DLS, Malvern Nanosizer 5000). Total silver concentrations were measured throughout the experiment at all sampling times by ICP-MS. For ICP-MS measurements, water samples were immediately filtered (Whatman nylon filters 0.2 mm) and acidified with 1% HNO_3 (65% suprapure, Merck) and analysed by ICP-MS. The Ag detection limit was 4.71 $\mu\text{g Ag/L}$. Free (dissolved) Ag^+ ions were analysed at all sampling times by immediate centrifugal ultrafiltration (Amicon Ultra Tubes, cut-off of 3kDa) of the samples to isolate the dissolved ions, with samples centrifuged for 30 min at 3,220 g, acidified with 1% HNO_3 (65% suprapure, Merck) and analysed by ICP-MS. The detection limit was 0.25 $\mu\text{g Ag/L}$. When values were below the detection limit, half of the detection limit value was used for data treatment (Helsel, 1990).

2.3. Biological endpoints

Ag accumulation in biofilms. At each sampling timepoint, two biofilm slides from each flume were extracted, scrapped and stored at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until their lyophilisation. Prior to lyophilisation, samples were stored at $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at least for 2h. After lyophilisation, samples were weighed (to obtain the **dry weight (DW)**, and thus, the biofilm biomass) and digested with 4 mL of 1% HNO_3 (65% suprapure, Merck) and 1 mL H_2O_2 (30% suprapure Merck) for 1 h at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Thereafter, samples were diluted to 15 mL with milli-Q water. After digestion, liquid samples were analysed by ICP-MS. The detection limit was 3.55 $\mu\text{g Ag/Kg}$. When the value was below the detection limit, half of the detection limit was also used for data treatment (Helsel, 1990).

Algal biomass (F_0) and **optimal photosynthetic activity (Φ_M)** were determined by measuring the biofilm chlorophyll a fluorescence emission with a pulse amplitude modulated fluorometer (miniPAM, Heinz Walz GmbH), using one slide from each flume following dark-acclimatisation (min 20 minutes) using the procedure of Corcoll et al. (2011). The optimal photosynthetic activity (Φ_M) or the maximal quantum yield is an estimate that provides information about the maximum electron flow, thus, maximum algal photosynthetic capacity. The units of both parameters are expressed in relative fluorescence units (rfu).

Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). From each flume, 2 microscope slides were collected at each sampling timepoint and scraped into a 2 mL vial, flash frozen and stored at -80 °C until analysis. EPS were measured using a total carbohydrate colorimetric assay kit (BioVison, Catalog #: K645), based on the phenol-sulfuric acid method in which polysaccharides are hydrolyzed and then converted to furfural or hydroxylfurfural. This assay can detect most forms of carbohydrates, including simple and complex saccharides, glycans, glycoproteins and glycolipids. Measurements were done after adapting the protocol to biofilm samples as follows. Firstly, biofilm samples were centrifuged at 13,000 g to remove excess water for 2 minutes, biofilms were gently homogenised using the assay buffer (200 µL), centrifuged again at 12,000 rpm for 5 minutes and 30 µL of supernatant (sample) was collected to perform the assay. Glucose standards were prepared according to the total carbohydrate colorimetric assay kit protocol. To start the hydrolysis reaction, 150 µL of concentrated H₂SO₄ (98%) was added to standards and samples, mixed for 1 minute on a shaker and incubated at 90 °C (using a heating block) for 15 minutes. After that time, 30 µL of Developer solution (from the test kit) was added, mixed for 5 minutes at room temperature. 250 µL of each sample and standard in triplicate were placed in a microplate reader and optical density was measured at 490 nm. For calculations, the value of the concentration 0 was subtracted from all readings. Results were expressed as µL total carbohydrate per µL of biofilm.

Respiration. The fluorescent “smart tracer” Resazurin (Raz, λEx 602 nm, λEm 616 nm), a metabolically active compound that transforms to Resorufin (Rru; λEx 570 nm, λEm 585 nm) under the mildly reducing conditions associated with the presence of aerobic microorganisms was used to quantify ecosystem respiration (Haggerty et al., 2008; Knapp et al., 2018) was used. The rate of Raz–Rru transformation can be used as an integrated measure of microbial respiration (Comer-Warner et al., 2018; González-pinzón et al., 2015) and is particularly well suited to outdoor mesocosms such as those used herein, as it directly measures respiration rather than the change in oxygen concentration (Baranov et al., 2016; Blaen et al., 2017). Stock solutions of Raz and Rru (100 mg/L) were made in the laboratory using ultra-pure water. Solutions were shaken on a rotary shaker for 30 mins to ensure the dye was completely dissolved, and flasks were wrapped in foil and stored in the fridge until required. A 60 mL injection of Raz (100 mg/L) was added as a pulse into each experimental flume, close to the pump, on three occasions (1, 15 and 30 days after the addition of silver) to raise the concentration to 100 µg/L. Samples of flume water (15 mL) were collected at 0, 1, 3, 6, 24 h post

Raz injection, passed through an 0.45 µm glass fibre filter and stored in 20 mL HDPE scintillation vials. All samples were stored in the dark at 5°C until analysis was undertaken, usually within 24 h of collection. Calibration standards for Raz and Rru (0, 5, 20, 50, 100 µg/L) were measured using a Cary Eclipse Spectrofluorometer (Varian Inc., Palo Alto, USA) with instrument settings as outlined in Khamis et al. (2015). A Raman blank was measured at the start of each instrument run to calibrate fluorescence intensity (Lawaetz & Stedmon, 2009). Excitation and emission were determined for each sample (plus an ultrapure water blank) over the excitation range 550–620 nm (2 nm slit width) and emission range 570–630 nm (2 nm slit width). Potential overlaps in fluorescence peaks were corrected following the method outlined by (Lemke et al., 2013). All samples were measured at 20°C and the pH of all samples was slightly alkaline (from 0 to 3 days 8.94 ± 1.05 in the 18 °C flumes and 9.01 ± 0.5 in the 25 °C flumes, and from 15 to 30 days 9.02 ± 0.82 and 8.43 ± 0.33 in the 18 °C and 25 °C flumes, respectively) and thus pH was not adjusted before measurement. Measurements of fluorescence intensity were converted into Raz (C_{Raz}) and Rru (C_{Rru}) concentrations using calibration curves, following the approach of Blaen et al. (2017). The slope of $\ln(C_{Rru}/C_{Raz} + 1)$ versus time was used as a surrogate for the aerobic respiration rate (Haggerty, 2013).

Extracellular enzyme activities (EEA), similar to EPS, EEA were analysed at each sampling time step. From each flume, 2 microscope slides were collected and their contents scraped into a 2 mL vial, flash frozen and stored at -80 °C until analysis. 15 mL of filtered water (nylon filters 0.2 µm pore size) was also collected from each flume and stored at -20 °C. EEA were assayed by means of fluorescent substrate analogues: β-Glucosidase (**Glu**; EC 3.2.1.21) which hydrolyses β-1,4 bonds of carbohydrates to provide cells with an organic carbon source, leucine aminopeptidase (**Leu**; EC 3.4.11.1) that cleaves peptides and supplies cells with a nitrogen source, and phosphatase (**Pho**; EC 3.1.3.1-2) which is responsible for the hydrolysis of organic phosphate esters, releasing inorganic phosphate that can be assimilated by micro-organisms and other life forms. Substrates (i.e., reference carbohydrate, peptides and phosphate esters) linked to 4-methylumbelliferyl (MUF) or aminomethyl-coumarin (AMC) were used to measure Glu (4-MUF-β-D-glucopyranoside), Pho (MUF-phosphatase) and Leu (L-leucine-AMC). EEA were analysed in both biofilm and water. For water, 2 mL of filtered water (nylon filters 0.2 µm pore size) was used and for biofilms the biofilm samples were resuspended in 2 mL filtered water (nylon filters 0.2 µm pore size) from their respective flume (treatment). In both cases, samples were incubated at saturating concentrations of their respective substrates (0.3 mM (Romaní

A.M., Sabater, 2001)), at their respective treatment temperature (18 °C and 25 °C) in the dark. Abiotic controls using autoclaved water and standard curves of MUF and AMC analogues were run in parallel during each assay. The enzymatic reactions were stopped after 50 min by adding 2 mL of 1M glycine buffer (pH 10.4) and centrifuging the biofilm suspensions for 10 min at 24,000g (Microcentrifuge 2417R, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). Aliquots of the supernatant (250 µL) were transferred to a black 96-well microplate (Greiner-Bio-One GmbH, Frickenhausen, Germany) to measure fluorescence (Tecan Spark 20M). The excitation and emission wavelengths were 365 and 455 nm (MUF-substrates) and 364 and 445 nm (AMC-substrate), respectively. The measurements of fluorescence intensity were converted to concentrations of substrate released (i.e., the products of the enzymatic degradation reactions on the reference carbohydrate, protein and phosphatase ester for Glu, Leu and Pho, respectively) based on their respective calibration curves (obtained by measuring fluorescence at concentrations ranging from 0 to 100 µM, expressed as a percentage of control).

2.4. Data analysis

Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare how (i) temperature, (ii) silver treatment and (iii) their combination, affected biofilm structure and function and water chemistry at acute (0, 1 and 3 days) and chronic (15 and 30 days) levels. All variables, except pH, were $\log(x+1)$ transformed to reduce skewed distributions. Homogeneity of variances and normality of data were checked prior to data analysis. If significant differences were found ($p < 0.05$), the ANOVA was followed by a Tukey-b test using a Bonferroni correction to control for multiple tests. These analyses were carried out using SPSS v26.

Variability in water quality parameters (temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, total nutrients – C, N and P – Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , total Ag and dissolved Ag^+) and biological responses (extracellular enzyme activities in water and biofilm, EPS, silver accumulated in biofilm, biofilm biomass (DW), algal biomass, photosynthetic activity) were examined using principal component analysis (PCA). Prior to analysis all data were $\log(x+1)$ transformed, standardized and centred. Two separate PCA analyses were undertaken on the biological and water quality parameters using the day 3 and day 30 data to assess acute and chronic effects, respectively. Data transformations were done using functions in base R (version 3.5.3) and the PCA analysis using was run the *factoextra* package.

To assess combined effects of T and Ag, we tested whether the combined effect of a pair of stressors (silver forms and temperature) had synergistic, antagonistic or additive effects, using the additive model (Crain et al., 2008), which compares the predicted additive effect of two stressors (i.e., the sum of each individual stressor) with the interaction effect of both stressors. We calculated individual, main and interaction effect sizes (Hedge's d (d)) for each stressor combination. Individual and main effects differ in those individual effects represent the response in the presence of a stressor alone vs. the control, while main effects compare the net effect of a stressor in the presence and absence of a second stressor, similar to main effects tests in ANOVA. Considering the direction of individual effects, we used the interaction effect size and 95% confidence interval to classify each silver and temperature combination as synergistic, antagonistic or additive (Crain et al., 2008) (see Effect size in the SI).

3. Results

3.1. Temporal changes in water chemistry and ENP characteristics during exposure under cool water conditions

Under current temperature scenarios (cool - T °C), the average water temperature throughout the experiment was 18.88 ± 1.22 °C. Electrical conductivity, DO, pH, Mg^{+2} , and Ca^{+2} did not differ between control flumes and those with silver (AgNP, Ag₂S NP and AgNO₃) at 18 °C. However, differences in nutrient concentrations were observed between those treatments at both acute and chronic timepoints. TP was significantly different between silver treatments, being higher in AgNO₃ and lower in the Ag₂S NP than in the control and Ag NP flumes at all timepoints (Fig. 1C, SI Table 1). For the chronic exposure period, TC concentrations were highest in Ag NP flumes, being 1.4 times higher than control and AgNO₃ flumes (Fig. 1A, SI Table 1) and TN only differed significantly between control and Ag NP flumes, being almost 1.5 times higher in Ag NP flumes (Fig. 1B, SI Table 1). Total silver concentrations in water (Ag_{total}) were significantly higher in the Ag NP flumes throughout the experiment (10 and 8 µg Ag/L in the acute and chronic period, respectively) while Ag^+ concentration showed differences over time (acute vs. chronic) and between silver flumes, mainly between Ag NP and AgNO₃ flumes. After 1 and 3 days (acute period), Ag^+ concentrations were significantly (1.75 times) higher in the AgNO₃ flumes (0.21 µg Ag^+ /L) than in the control and Ag₂S NP flumes (below detection limit, 0.12 µg Ag^+ /L), while in the Ag NP flume the Ag^+ concentration was 1.4 times higher than the control flumes but this difference was not statistically significant. After 15 and 30 days (chronic exposure period), Ag^+ concentration in water showed the highest values in AgNP flumes (0.28 µg Ag^+ /L), followed by

AgNO₃ flumes (0.17 µg Ag⁺/L) while Ag⁺ concentration in control and Ag₂S NP flumes were below the detection limit (<0.12 µg Ag⁺/L) (SI Table 1). Based on the size measurements, agglomeration of ENPs was apparent throughout the experiment in the 18 °C flumes, with average size and standard deviation of particles from all silver flumes (Ag NP, Ag₂S NP, and AgNO₃) was 463 ± 16.7 nm with zeta potentials of -20.10 ± 0.71 mV with no significant differences irrespective of the starting form of the Ag.

3.2. Temporal impacts of warm temperature on water physiochemistry and ENP properties

Under the elevated temperature conditions (ΔT °C), the average water temperature throughout the experiment was 26.75 ± 1.20 °C. Electrical conductivity, Mg⁺² and Ca⁺² were significantly (1.2 times) higher under warm condition (ΔT °C) than at the cooler one (T °C). DO was significantly lower in the ΔT°C flumes (1.2 times) (SI Table 1). Increased water temperatures also affected nutrient concentrations in the flumes: TN were significantly higher (1.5 times) in ΔT°C flumes than in T°C flumes (Fig. 1B, SI Table 1). After 1 and 3 days of treatment, a spike in TP concentration was statistically significant (205% increase) in ΔT°C flumes relative to T°C treatments, but this equalised after 15 and 30 days being no more significant between different temperatures (Fig. 1C, SI Table 1). However, after 15 and 30 days, pH and TC, were significantly lower in ΔT°C flumes than T°C ones (Fig. 1A, SI Table 1). Finally, Ag⁺ concentration and Ag_{total} concentration in water only responded to the increase of temperature after 15 and 30 days, being lower in the ΔT°C flumes (SI Table 1). Particle sizes were higher in all silver-containing flumes at ΔT°C than at T °C, being smallest in the Ag₂S NP (579.76 ± 66.33 nm), followed by AgNO₃ (763.33 ± 72.89 nm) and largest in Ag NP (782.33 ± 29.59 nm) (ANOVA, F = 40.43, p < 0.0001). The particles' zeta potential in silver flumes at ΔT°C decreased significantly (by around 62.53 % to -12.57 ± 1.43 mV) compared to the surface charges in the T°C flumes (ANOVA, F = 21.64, p < 0.0001) but did not differ between silver treatments.

3.3. ENP impacts on biofilms under the cool temperature conditions

Based on two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), exposure to different silver treatments (Ag NP, Ag₂S NP and AgNO₃) under current (cool) temperatures affected biofilm structure and function at both, acute and chronic scales (Fig 1 and 3, SI Table 2). Of the 12 biofilm parameters analysed, 7 showed significant differences due to exposure to the various silver treatments at the end of the experiment. Glu in biofilms decreased significantly during chronic period in Ag₂S NP and AgNO₃ treatments as compared to the control, while the impacts of exposure to Ag NP

treatment were similar to the control (Fig.1G). Moreover, Glu measured in water was also affected by chronic exposures, resulting in higher values in Ag NP flumes and, surprisingly, lower values in the AgNO₃ flumes (Fig. 1D). Pho expression in biofilm also decreased in AgNO₃ flumes with respect to controls but showed the highest values in the Ag₂S NP flumes during chronic exposures (Figs. 1I). Ag_{acc} concentrations in biofilms increased over time in all silver treatments (Fig. 2A). From the beginning to the end of the experiment, Ag_{acc} concentrations increased almost by 400% in Ag NP flumes, by 260% in AgNO₃ and 150% in Ag₂S NP treated flumes. Control flumes did not show any Ag_{acc}, indicating that there was no silver contamination throughout the experiment. After 1 and 3 days, Ag_{acc} was significantly higher only in Ag NP flumes compared to controls, while at the end of the experiment Ag_{acc} was significantly higher in Ag NP and AgNO₃ flumes (Fig. 2A). EPS concentrations did not increase over time in any silver treatment or in the control flumes but retained the pattern of EPS levels present after the biofilm conditioning and initial spiking with the silver treatments, whereby the highest EPS concentrations were in Ag NP flumes, followed by the Ag₂S NP and control flumes, and lowest in AgNO₃ flumes during the experiment (Fig. 2C). Respiration (only measured at chronic timepoints) was lowest in the Ag NP and AgNO₃ flumes, and highest in the control and Ag₂S flumes (Fig. 2D). F₀ was highest in the Ag NP flumes and lowest in AgNO₃ flumes after 3 days. No difference in F₀ was observed due to silver treatments after 30 days (Fig. 2E). Leu activity in water and biofilm (Fig. 1E and H), Pho activity in water (Fig. 1F), photosynthetic activity (Fig. 2F), and biofilm biomass (Fig. 2E) did not differ between control and silver treatments.

3.4. Effect of increased temperature on biofilm structure and function

Significant effects of warm temperature (25° - ΔT °C) on a range of biofilm properties were determined by ANOVA (Figs. 1 and 2, SI Table 3). After 1 and 3 days, the ΔT°C caused a statistically significant decrease of μg Ag_{acc}. per biofilm biomass, decreasing by 1.5 times as compared to that at cool T°C (Fig. 2A). On the contrary, biofilm biomass (DW) increased ≈ 2.4-fold and Φ_M increased by 1.7 as compared to the T°C scenario (Fig. 2B and 2F, respectively). At acute exposure times, effects were observed on all extracellular enzyme activities. In water, Glu, Leu and Pho showed a significantly higher activity in ΔT°C flumes, being 1, 1.4, and 115 times higher than in the T°C flumes, respectively (Fig. 1D, 1E, 1F). In the biofilms, Glu and Leu activity decreased by 50% and 75%, respectively in ΔT°C flumes compared to the controls, whereas Pho showed a 9-fold increase in the ΔT°C flumes (Fig. 1G, H, I). After 15 and 30 days of exposure, ΔT°C significantly increased Leu and Pho activity in water, being almost 2 and 10 times more

active than in the T°C flumes (Fig. 1E, F, respectively). Moreover, Pho also showed higher activity in biofilm treatments in ΔT°C flumes, being 8 times higher than the Pho activity in T°C flumes (Fig. 1I). Enhanced biofilm respiration, (+30%) was found in ΔT°C flumes compared to that in the T°C flumes (Fig. 2D). Biofilm $A_{g_{acc}}$, biofilm biomass, photosynthetic activity, Glu in water and in biofilm and Leu in biofilm did not display significant differences between T°C and ΔT°C treatments during chronic exposures. EPS and algal biomass did not respond to ΔT°C for any type of exposure, acute or chronic.

3.5. Combined effects of ENP exposure and warm temperature on biofilm performance

The PCA of the physicochemical data (Fig. 3A) explained > 55 % of the variance with 2 axes. PC 1 (variance = 35.3%) represents a nutrient and ions concentration gradient separating acute and chronic samples. PC 2 (variance = 23.1%) separates the control and silver flumes according to nutrient concentrations and temperature. While conductivity and main cations (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) were important variables for cool flumes at acute timepoints, nutrients (TN and TP) dominate the chronic behaviour. In warm flumes, acute physicochemical parameters were characterised by high oxygen concentration, TC, and pH while chronic parameters were associated with high TP. The PCA of the biological variables is displayed in Fig. 3B with the first axis (29.5% of the variance) representing a gradient of enzymatic activity in biofilm separating T°C from ΔT°C flumes. The second axis of the PCA explains 18.2% of the variance and is also an enzymatic axis but this time the enzymatic activities in water and $A_{g_{acc}}$ in biofilm. This second axis shows a clear difference between the acute and chronic periods especially in the T°C flumes.

For all measured parameters the main effects, i.e., the comparison between the net effect of silver under cool (DAg, DA g_2S and DA gNO_3) and warm water temperatures (DΔT:AgNP, DΔT:Ag $_2S$ NP, DΔT:Ag NO_3) and their interaction (DIΔT:AgNP, DIΔT:Ag $_2S$ NP, DIΔT:Ag NO_3), resulted in additive responses (SI Table 3 and SI Fig. 5). When considering individual effects (the response in the presence of a stressor alone vs. the control), almost half of the 24 parameters measured (conductivity, oxygen, pH, TC, TN, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Ag^+ , respiration, Glu in biofilm, Leu in water and biofilm and EPS) showed additive responses (54.17%) i.e., the combined responses were equivalent to the sum of the individual effects of silver (in whatever form) and temperature, while the rest of the treatments showed synergistic (combined effects greater than the sum of the individual effects) and/or antagonistic (combined effects less than sum of the individual effects) interaction in all or some silver forms (Table 2, SI Table 4). AgNP+ΔT°C caused more

synergistic effects (29.17%) than antagonistic ones (8.33%). Synergies were found in TP, NP size, total Ag, biofilm biomass, Pho activity in water, algal biomass and photosynthetic activity while antagonistic effects were found in Ag_{acc} in biofilm and Pho activity in biofilm. Ag_2S NP+ $\Delta T^\circ C$ also caused more synergistic effects than antagonistic (20.83% vs. 16.67%). Again, TP, biofilm biomass, Pho activity in water, and photosynthetic activity showed synergistic responses while NP size, Ag_{acc} in biofilm, Glu activity in water, and algal biomass were antagonistic. Finally, $AgNO_3 + \Delta T^\circ C$ caused slightly more antagonistic responses than synergistic ones (20.85% vs. 16.67%). In this case, zeta potential (of particles produced *in situ* during the exposures as only ionic Ag^+ was present initially), biofilm biomass, Pho activity in biofilm and photosynthetic activity showed a synergistic interaction while TP, NP size, Ag_{acc} , Pho activity in water, and algal biomass displayed antagonistic interaction responses.

4. Discussion

This study examined the effects of different silver forms (pristine Ag NP, aged Ag_2S NP, and ionic $AgNO_3$) and increased water temperature on freshwater biofilm communities. We tested the following hypotheses: (i) different forms of silver nanomaterials — pristine Ag NP, aged Ag_2S NP, and ionic $AgNO_3$ — exert distinct impacts on biofilm communities; (ii) increased water temperature influences both biological aspects (biofilm composition and functioning) and physicochemical parameters (nanoparticle size, dissolution behaviour, and microcosm conditions such as nutrient concentrations and organic matter sources); and (iii) the combined stressors of silver and temperature increase (ΔT°) produce synergistic effects, that amplify the individual impacts on biofilm structure and functioning. The findings reveal distinct impacts driven by the interaction between silver forms and temperature, with notable implications for biofilm functioning and resilience.

4.1. Temperature effects on silver ENP physicochemical properties and transformations

Temperature directly influenced silver nanoparticle (ENP) behavior, primarily through agglomeration and reduced dissolution in the mesocosms. The silver accumulation (Ag_{acc}) in biofilms was substantial despite low silver concentrations (50 $\mu g/L$ for Ag NP and $AgNO_3$, and 25 $\mu g/L$ for Ag_2S NP). The maximum Ag_{acc} values were 266.81 and 926.14 $\mu g/gDW$ in Ag NP flumes (cool and warm temperatures, respectively), and 166.37 and 184.81 $\mu g/gDW$ in $AgNO_3$ flumes. In contrast, Ag_2S NP flumes exhibited lower Ag_{acc} values (91.79 and 98.59 $\mu g/gDW$, respectively), aligning with Ag_2S NP's low solubility and reduced toxic potential.

The PVP coating on the 60 nm AgNPs, known for enhancing nanoparticle stability (see McGillicuddy et al., 2017b), did not prevent agglomeration upon mesocosm introduction. Elevated temperatures ($\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$) further facilitated agglomeration by reducing zeta potential, indicative of charge neutralization. The warm flumes increased divalent cation concentrations (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}), likely driven by thermal equilibrium adjustments and enhanced biofilm metabolism, also promoted ENP aggregation (McGillicuddy et al., 2017b; Zhang et al., 2016). These cations decreased electrostatic repulsion, increasing particle size and reducing Ag^+ ion release (Huang et al., 2016). Additionally, divalent cations may form ion bridges between silver ENPs and biofilm biomacromolecules (e.g., with lipopolysaccharides on the bacterial surface), altering membrane permeability and facilitating particles or ions uptake into the cells (Huang et al., 2016).

Elevated temperatures also indirectly influenced silver ENP transformations by enhancing biofilm metabolic activity, which increased extracellular enzyme production (Pho and Leu) in water. While EPS can stabilize or destabilize nanoparticles, this study found no temperature-related differences in EPS content.

4.2. Effects of silver ENPs and Ag^+ ions on biofilm function

ENP exposure altered freshwater biofilm functions, enabling higher silver uptake compare to Ag^+ diffusion, likely facilitated by increased Glu activity in Ag NP than AgNO_3 flumes. Elevated EPS concentration in the Ag NP and Ag_2S NP flumes (compared to the AgNO_3 ones) could boost this process since ENPs bind biomolecules from the surrounding environment due to their high surface-to-mass ratio. For instance, Ag NP (around 38-73 nm) while unable to enter algal cells, bind extracellular proteins, inhibiting enzyme activity (Yue et al., 2017) and forming a “protein corona” or eco-corona with co-pollutants (Lynch et al., 2009, 2014; Markiewicz et al., 2018; Nasser et al., 2020). This corona act as a Trojan horse, facilitating particle uptake via endocytosis (Luoma, 2008; Park et al., 2010). Once internalised, silver ENPs oxidize to Ag^+ , enhancing antibacterial activity (Durán et al., 2016). Higher Ag_{acc} in Ag NP flumes suggests EPS and microbial exudates modified ENPs, amplifying their toxicity. This study confirms ENP-specific effects (Ag NP and Ag_2S NP), including enzyme inhibition, through particle-mediated mechanisms distinct from those observed with AgNO_3 flumes (Huang et al., 2016; Navarro et al., 2008; Tlili, Cornut, Behra, Gil-Allué, et al., 2016).

Acute exposures (1 - 3 days) cause minimal effects on biofilm function. Instead, they caused variations in structural components like EPS - in Ag NP flumes, 1.23 time higher than control

ones and in AgNO₃ flumes, 0.3 times less than controls - and in algal biomass - 0.3 times less in AgNO₃ flumes than control flumes - reinforcing the distinct impacts of silver particles and ions. Increased EPS in Ag NP flumes likely represents a protective mechanism mainly driven by algal communities, whereas AgNO₃ exposure negatively affected biofilms properties, possibly due to bacterial inhiation and subsequent EPS reduction (Das et al., 2012). Moreover, the high TP values in AgNO₃ flumes may stem microbial death and phosphorous release during decomposition. However, Pho activity remained unaffected, consistent with studies on Ag NP exposure (50 µg/L) that showed no impact on enzymatic activities like Glu, Leu and Pho or respiration after 5 days (Tlili et al., 2017). Contrasting results in acute Ag NP and Ag⁺ exposure is attributed to variations in exposure concentrations (from 50 µg/L to 20 mg/L), microbial communities (biofilms, heterotrophic biofilms, bacterioplankton), water chemistry (nutrients, minerals) and environmental conditions (e.g., temperature and light/darkness) (Das et al., 2012; Gil-Allué et al., 2015; Tlili, Cornut, Behra, Gil-Allué, et al., 2016). In this study, significant Ag_{acc.} after 3 days, neither ENPs nor free Ag⁺ ions, did not affect enzymatic activity (Glu, Pho, Leu, or photosynthesis), possibly due to EPS-mediated tolerance, as observed with titanium dioxide (Hou et al., 2019), allowing biofilms to cope with silver toxicity.

Chronic exposure (15-30 days) to silver resulted in significant functional and structural biofilm impacts. Glu activity in biofilm was decreased by both Ag₂S NP and AgNO₃ silver forms while in the water only by AgNO₃. Ag₂S NPs increased Pho activity in biofilms but reduced total phosphorous (TP), indicating a functional biofilm resilience despite low silver solubility and toxicity. Thus, Ag₂S NP play a functional role in regulating the biofilm enzyme activity despite these flumes having similar EPS concentrations and biofilm Ag_{acc.} values to the control flumes. Respiration was reduced in both Ag NP (23%) and AgNO₃ (15%) flumes, consistent with previous findings (Tlili et al., 2017). Both silver forms (particle and ion), directly or indirectly, interfere with electron transport chains or damage cellular membranes, generating reactive oxygen species and altering redox chemistry leading to a reduction of respiration.

4.3. Effects of temperature on biofilm functions

Acute ΔT°C exposure (+8 °C) enhanced biofilm biomass (2.5-fold), photosynthetic activity (Φ_M 1.7-fold) and all enzyme activities measured in water and Pho measured in biofilm. These changes correlated with increased nutrients (TN and TP) and improved algal health, increasing the substrate (e.g., peptides) available for Leu (Sand-Jensen et al., 2007; Ylla et al., 2009). However, Glu and Leu activities within the biofilm decreased, highlighting enzyme-specific

responses. The co-occurrence of temperature and nutrients could also increase enzyme activities as both factors together are the main drivers of increased biofilm growth (Degerman et al., 2013; Díaz Villanueva et al., 2011; Ylla et al., 2009).

Chronic temperature exposure ($\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ flumes) maintained elevated Pho and Leu activities in water and biofilm, along with increased respiration. Leu activity likely rose due to nitrogen substrate availability, reduced total carbon (TC), and biofilm-driven nutrient cycling as due to a greater use of released algal peptides and organic phosphorous compounds over polysaccharides (C source exclusively) (Romaní et al., 2014). Contrary to expectations, no significant temperature effects on biofilm biomass or algal biomass were observed, consistent with previous studies (Pesce et al., 2018). Elevated temperature primarily influenced heterotrophic activity, shifting ecosystem function towards respiration over primary production (Demars et al., 2011; Díaz Villanueva et al., 2011; Romaní et al., 2014; Sand-Jensen et al., 2007; Ylla et al., 2014), leading to a strong decrease in biofilm compositional diversity after 4 weeks (Morin et al., 2017; Pesce et al., 2018).

4.4. Combined effects of silver ENPs, Ag^+ ions and increased water temperature on biofilm functions

Combined stressors – silver ENP and warm temperature – produced additive effects (62.5%) predominantly, with synergistic (22.2%) exceeding antagonistic interactions (15.3%). The prevalence of additive effects is consistent with previously published research (Elbrecht et al., 2016; Piggott et al., 2015; Romero et al., 2019). Pristine (Ag NP) and aged ENPs (Ag_2S NP) combined with $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ had more synergistic effects (29.2% and 20.8%, respectively) than Ag^+ (16.7%). Ag^+ exhibited more antagonistic interactions (20.8%), indicating distinct mechanisms. The occurrence of antagonistic effects has been described at the community level in freshwater ecosystems (Côté et al., 2016; Jackson et al., 2016), and may result from in situ particle precipitation during ionic exposure, reducing metal toxicity (Skladnev et al., 2020). It is interesting to highlight that the same metal (silver) but in an alternative form (particle vs. ion), produces different biofilm interactions and thus, different impacts on freshwater ecosystems. Temperature and ENPs (irrespective of the silver ENP form, pristine or aged) synergistically influenced phosphorus cycling, increasing TP and Pho activity in ENP flumes. Ag_{acc} increased synergistically under Ag NP + $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ exposure, while additive effects were observed with Ag_2S NP + $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ and Ag^+ + $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$. At the same time, Ag_2S NP + $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ exposure had an antagonistic effect on the Glu activity in water while additive effects of this activity were observed for Ag NP + $\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$

and $\text{Ag}^+ + \Delta T$ °C. These findings agree with previous research on biofilms measured directly in streams that found that Glu activity and metal tolerance increase during warm seasons (Faburé et al., 2015). Understanding the exact reasons for this negative interaction warrants future research into the molecular mechanisms of the impacts.

Functional parameters (e.g., respiration, photosynthesis) mainly showed additive or synergistic responses, whereas community-level responses (e.g., biomass) often displayed antagonism (Côté et al., 2016). Synergistic effects of combined stressors on biofilm and algal biomass suggest higher water temperatures amplify silver toxicity, reducing biofilm tolerance to metals (Lambert et al., 2016; Morin et al., 2015). Conversely, bacterial tolerance to metals can increase with temperature shifts, as seen in heterotrophic biofilms (Pesce et al., 2018). Seasonal metal pollution may also mask biofilm antioxidant capacity, highlighting ΔT °C's role in increasing biofilm vulnerability to metal toxicity (Bonet et al., 2013).

Finally, a graphical summary (Fig. 4) illustrates the distinct impacts of pristine Ag NPs and aged Ag_2S NP on biofilms, driven by variations in Ag^+ ion release, interactions with EPS, internalization pathways, and silver accumulation. Temperature primarily affected biofilm functionality, such as respiration and enzyme activities, rather than structural parameters, with these effects influenced by microcosm conditions, community dynamics, and silver transformations. Combined stressors (silver and temperature) largely resulted in additive effects, with synergistic responses being more common for ENPs, while antagonistic interactions were more prevalent for ionic silver.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that different forms of silver nanomaterials (pristine Ag NPs, aged Ag_2S NPs, and ionic AgNO_3) exert distinct impacts on freshwater biofilm communities (e.g. nutrient cycling), highlighting the critical role of silver speciation and environmental conditions. Pristine Ag NPs and aged Ag_2S NPs showed unique effects on biofilm functioning, driven by differences in Ag^+ ion release, interactions with extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), internalization mechanisms, and silver accumulation. Temperature was a key factor influencing silver nanoparticle behaviour, promoting agglomeration and reducing dissolution, while also enhancing biofilm metabolic activity and enzyme production.

Acute silver exposure primarily affected structural parameters like EPS and algal biomass, while chronic exposure significantly impaired biofilm respiration and enzymatic activities, underscoring the importance of exposure duration. Combined stressors (silver and

temperature) predominantly caused additive effects, with synergistic interactions more frequent for engineered nanoparticles (ENPs) and antagonistic responses more common for ionic silver. Elevated temperatures amplified the toxicity of silver, reducing biofilm tolerance to metals and shifting ecosystem functionality toward respiration rather than primary production.

Although our results should be interpreted prudently at the ecosystem level and as an extrapolation in a global scale context, these findings highlight the vulnerability of biofilms to silver nanoparticle pollution under warming scenarios, emphasizing the complex interplay between nanoparticle transformations, microbial community dynamics, and environmental conditions. Seasonal temperature fluctuations and warming trends exacerbate the ecological impacts of silver nanomaterials, with significant implications for freshwater ecosystem health. Understanding these interactions is essential for predicting the ecological impacts of nanomaterials in freshwater ecosystems, particularly under the combined pressures of global change and anthropogenic pollution. Future research should focus on elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying these effects and their implications for ecosystem resilience and how can affect ecosystem nutrient cycling (including carbon balance). Finally, data from this study should be taken into consideration to improve risk assessment policies and regulations and, in particular, previous consensus about the stability or non-toxicity of Ag₂SNPs in aquatic environments should be reconsidered.

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